

Ruminal Acidosis– An Overview

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Abstract

A drop in ruminal pH is a common definition of ruminal acidosis. The most frequent cause of the disease is the sudden ingestion of toxic doses of carbohydrate-rich feed, such as grain. Change in microbial population occurs, particularly Gram+ bacteria like *Streptococcus bovis*. Lactic acid increases, pH decreases to 5 which destroys protozoa, cellulolytic, and lactate-utilizing organisms and impairs rumen motility. Enlarged rumen, hypermotility, abdominal pain, etc. includes the clinical signs. This article gives an overview of the etiology, pathogenesis, clinical signs, and treatment of ruminal acidosis.

Introduction

Ruminal acidosis is a fermentation disorder in the rumen characterized by a lower-than-normal ruminal pH, but reflecting an imbalance between microbial production, microbial utilization, and ruminal absorption of volatile fatty acids (VFA) Ingestion of a large amount of fermentable carbohydrate. Cattle that accidentally gain access to the large quantity of readily digested carbohydrates particularly grains. Change in the microbial population, particularly Gram+ bacteria like *Streptococcus bovis*. Lactic acid increases, pH decreases to 5 which destroys protozoa, cellulolytic, and lactate-utilizing organisms and impairs rumen motility. Dehydration results from an increase in osmotic pressure and excessive fluid movement in the rumen (Jaramillo *et al.*, 2017).

Salivary buffers or ammonia formed when urea enters through the ruminal wall neutralizing between 30 and 50 percent of the acid in the rumen. Approximately a smaller amount continues into the lower gastrointestinal tract. However, even the most conservative estimates leave a significant proportion of about 30–50% of the acid that is ruminally produced and that has to be absorbed by the ruminal wall, and one of the most important reasons for the appearance of ruminal acidosis would be a decrease in the absorptive capacity of the rumen which is thus unable

to maintain a stable pH. Absorption of VFA, by removing unionized acid and by the exchange of ionized VFA for bicarbonate during the absorption process, aids in maintaining pH near neutrality. Consequently, a reduced rate of VFA absorption causes ruminal pH to drop for two reasons: ruminal VFA accumulates and bicarbonate input from the bloodstream is decreased. The severity of acidosis allows us to classify ruminal acidosis considering different factors, among others, like ruminal pH threshold, predominant acid (VFA or lactic), and ruminal population bacteria, in two forms: acute and subacute acidosis. In acute forms, symptoms will appear in the animal, more or less noticeable, and will be absent in a subacute form. Taking into account ruminal parameters, ruminal pH will be low in acute form, and this fact will imply an important difference in bacterial species, with gram-negative bacteria appearing, with lactate consumers bacteria, and a high amount of VFA. Meanwhile, in an acute form, we will find gram-positive bacteria, with lactate producer bacteria, like the amount of serum lactate and decreasing the presence of lactate in the rumen. In conclusion, we can define acute ruminal acidosis as a metabolic status defined by a decrease in blood pH, parallel to blood bicarbonate decrease, which is caused by a D-lactic ruminal overproduction. *Streptococcus bovis* or even, in ruminal pH below 4.8, *Lactobacillus* spp. In this severe form, with pH next to the isoelectric point of lactic acid (around 3.8), we will find metabolic acidosis, with a decrease in blood pH and blood bicarbonate.

Pathogenesis of acute lactic acidosis

Changes in rumen microflora

Ingestion of excessive quantities of highly fermentable feeds by a ruminant is followed within 2-6 hours by a marked change in the microbial population in the rumen. There is an increase in the number of *Streptococcus bovis* which utilize carbohydrates to produce large quantities of lactic acid. Continuous production of lactic acid results in the reduction of rumen pH to 5 or less, which destroys cellulolytic bacteria and protozoa.

Volatile fatty acids and lactic acid in the rumen

The concentration of volatile fatty acids increases initially contributing to the decrease in the ruminal pH. The low pH allows lactobacilli to use the large quantities of carbohydrates in the rumen to produce an excessive amount of lactic acid, resulting in ruminal lactic acidosis. Both D and L forms of the acid are produced, which markedly increase ruminal osmolality, and water is drawn from the systemic circulation, causing haemoconcentration and dehydration. Ruminal osmolality increases from the normal of 280mosmol/L to almost 400mosmol/L. Some of the lactic acid is buffered by ruminal buffers but large amounts are absorbed by the rumen and some move

into and are absorbed further down the intestinal tract. As the rumen pH declines, the amplitude and frequency of rumen contractions are reduced and at about pH of 5, there is ruminal atony.

Systemic lactic acidosis

The absorbed lactic acid is buffered by the plasma bicarbonate buffering system. In severe cases of lactic acidosis, the reserves of plasma bicarbonate are reduced, the blood pH declines steadily, and the blood pressure declines, causing a decrease in perfusion pressure and oxygen supply to peripheral tissues and resulting in a further increase in lactic acidosis from cellular respiration. Both, D and L lactic acids are produced. The L lactic acid is utilized more rapidly than the D isomer which accumulates and causes severe D lactic acidosis.

Subacute ruminal acidosis

Subacute ruminal acidosis (SARA) in dairy cattle is a disorder of ruminal fermentation in dairy cattle caused by the ingestion of large amounts of concentrates and inadequate amounts of fiber administered to increase milk production in early lactation.

Periparturient cows are at risk due to:

- a) Concentrate intake increases
- b) The time required for rumen microflora to adapt
- c) Deficiency of fibre in the diet
- d) Error in delivery of ration

SARA is considered to reduce milk fat to protein ratio (FPR) below 1. In acidic rumen fermentation products such as trans 10, and cis 12 conjugated linoleic acid are produced which are considered to be potent inhibitors of mammary de novo fat synthesis (Bauman *et al.*, 2008).

Manipulation of acid-base balance

A basic understanding of acid-base balance suggests that additional dietary sodium bicarbonate could be beneficial to counteract a high risk of subacute rumen acidosis (SARA). However, as in dietary cation-anion balance (DCAB), sodium itself has an alkalinizing effect, as more complete theories of acid-base balance suggest that pH itself is merely an easily measured proxy of a more complex ionic balance. This may explain the reported beneficial effects of positive DCAB diets on the dry matter intake of post parturient cows, and provides an alternative strategy to counteract a high risk of rumen pH depression.

The rumen pH will fluctuate between acidic and normal pH. The condition can be termed as SARA if the ruminal pH of 5.6 is maintained over a period of three hours This condition is common in cattle during the periparturient period. Ruminal acidosis is considered subacute when

the low ruminal pH is caused by excessive accumulation of volatile fatty acids without persistent lactic acid accumulation, and when the low ruminal pH (5.5 or below maintained for more than 3 hours in a day) is restored to normal by the animal's physiologic responses. Characterized by occasional lowering and normal ruminal pH.

Clinical findings

- Enlarged rumen, hypermotility, Abdominal pain
- Hydro rumen; accumulation of organic acids and glucose increases the osmotic pressure inside the rumen, resulting in water flux from the bloodstream across the rumen wall
- Simple indigestion- rapidly fatal acidemia and strong metabolic acidosis
- Laminitis-

SARA can induce various complications or sequelae, including diarrhoea (more than 30% of animals on a farm will have diarrhea- faeces contains undigested grains, fibres, and fibrin clots), laminitis, poor body condition, abscesses without any obvious causes, haemoptysis or epistaxis and abomasal diseases in ruminants.

The principles of treatment are

1. Correct the ruminal and systemic acidosis and prevent further production of lactic acid
2. Restore fluid and electrolyte losses and maintain circulating blood volumes
3. Restore forestomach and intestinal motility to normal

4. Correct the ruminal and systemic acidosis and prevent further production of lactic acid

Management

- Slowly degradable starch sources such as maize pose a lower risk than sugars, wheat, or barley
- More rapidly digestible fibre encourages high dry matter intake and allows higher milk yield to be maintained, lowering the risk of acidosis
- Sufficient dietary sodium is required to absorb VFAs and the requirement is likely to increase when lactate is pre more
- Restricted water intake for 24 hours
- Probiotics (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *L. plantarum*) reduce organic acid accumulation and might decrease the risk of subacute ruminal acidosis (SARA) (Hiroko *et al.*, 2016)

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